

FAN, TA'LIM, MADANIYAT VA INNOVATSIYA

[Jild: 03 Nashr: 7 (2024)] ISSN: 2992-8915

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

THE HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE EARLY NOMADS OF CENTRAL ASIA

*Isarov Umidulla*¹

¹Teacher of Termez State University

Abstract: The history of nomadic pastoral communities in Central Asia is crucial for understanding the region's ancient past. This historiographical review covers the development of nomadic cultures from the Mesolithic through the Bronze Age, highlighting significant archaeological research and scholarly debates about the nomadic societies of Central Asia.

Keywords: Nomadic Pastoralism, Central Asia, Bronze Age, Andronovo culture, Tozabagyab culture, Amirabad culture, Kayrakkum culture, archaeological research, cultural exchange, migration patterns, pastoral tribes, ethnic interactions.

Introduction. The study of nomadic pastoral communities in Central Asia is pivotal for understanding the region's historical evolution. The roots of animal husbandry trace back to the Mesolithic period with the domestication of wild animals, which expanded during the Neolithic period and became a distinct economic sector by the Bronze Age. This historiography examines key archaeological findings and scholarly interpretations concerning the development of nomadic pastoral cultures in Central Asia. The study of the history of the emergence of nomadic pastoral communities and their development in different historical periods is great importance in the science of history. The historical roots of the emergence of animal husbandry, according to historical data, were formed in the Mesolithic period. The domestication of wild animals began during this period.

During the Neolithic period, domestic animal husbandry flourished, and it is observed that it grew to a certain extent by the Neolithic period. After the second social division of labor, domestic animal husbandry became the basis for a separate economy. And by the Bronze Age, animal husbandry had developed as a separate economic sector. In the foothills, deserts, steppes, and semi-steppes of Central Asia, many cultures have been formed, the basis of nomadic pastoralism.

Methods and methodology of research. The methodology for analyzing the historiography of the early nomads of Central Asia involves a comprehensive approach to understanding and interpreting historical

research and archaeological findings related to nomadic pastoral societies in the region. This approach includes several key components: literature review, historical and archaeological analysis, comparative analysis, critical analysis.

This methodology provides a systematic framework for understanding the historiographical development of the study of early nomads in Central Asia, ensuring a thorough and balanced analysis of the field's academic evolution.

Results. A large part of Central Asia is covered by foothills and steppe areas. If we look at the natural and economic map of Central Asia, the foothills of the Tien Shan, Pamir, Alay, Gissar, Zarafshan, Sultan Uvays, the western part of southern Turkmenistan, the basins of the Amudarya, Syrdarya and Zarafshan rivers and adjacent territories formed a semi-steppe zone. These areas have always been rich in food for livestock. The pastoral population is spread over the above-mentioned areas in order to increase the number of livestock. For this reason, these areas for archaeologists have become objects of study of cultures created by nomadic pastoralists.

In the study of monuments created by the first nomadic pastoralists of Central Asia, S.P. Tolstov, B.A. Litvinskiy, A.N. Bernshtam, A.M. Mandelshtam, A.Terenojkin, V.Pyankov, Yu.F. Buryakov, A. Askarov, Sh.Shaydullaev, N.A.Avanesova, E.E. Kuzmina, A. Itina, K.A.Akischev, K.Baypakov conducted large-scale archeological researches and focused on the development of nomadic cattle breeding and their relations with the settled population. According to archeological research, by the second millennium BC, the central and northwestern part of Central Asia became the site of settlement of nomadic pastoral tribes. Archeologist V.I. Sarianidi's research notes that by the second millennium BC, the Bronze Age of Central Asia had become a place of migration for nomadic tribes [10, p. 57-58.]. In this period, the owners of the Yogocho band culture lived in northwestern Central Asia and the owners of the Andronovo culture lived in the northeast Central Asia. Nomadic animal husbandry was their main occupation. According to archeological research, from the middle of the second millennium BC, this steppe population began to enter the lower basins of the Syrdarya from the northeast of Central Asia. Initially, they settled in the lower basins of the Amudarya (Tozabogyob, Amirabad, Suvyorgan cultures). Some of them enter the middle basin of the Syrdarya, South Kazakhstan and the Tashkent oasis. Later they spread through the Yettisuv to the Fergana Valley (Kayrakkum culture) and from there to Ustrushana and Sogdiana [2, p. 27].

After the owners of the Andronovo culture or Andronovo historical-cultural unit settled in the South Akchadarya, a new generation was formed as a result of mixing with the local population. As a result of this ethnic mixture, the unique cultures of Suvyorgan, Tozabagyab and Amirabad were formed.

Archaeological research in these cultures was carried out by archaeologists such as S.P. Tolstov, M.A. Itina, B. Vaynberg [12, p. 66-68]. The material sources of the Andronovo and Tozabagyab cultures - crafts, tools of labor and hunting, the technique of building houses, and even the practice of digging graves and burying corpses - are similar. As a result of the adaptation of the population to local conditions, the owners of the Tozabagyab culture settle; archaeological sources indicate that they mastered agriculture.

Researchers note that some of the tribes that created the Andronovo and Srub cultures also invaded the Tashkent oasis during the Bronze Age [5, p. 39-41]. Archeologist researcher A.G. Maksimova concluded that she belonged to the Bronze Age based on the analysis of material objects obtained as a result of archeological excavations in the cemeteries on the borders of Saryogoch and Shimkent [8, p. 175-176.]. In 1955-1957, A.I. Terenojkin found material objects of the Bronze Age around Burchimulla and concluded that they belonged to the end of the second millennium BC - the beginning of the first millennium. [11, p. 270-281]

In 1964-1965, J. Duke opened several tombs in connection with the construction of the Charvak Reservoir, from which he was able to obtain bronze bow arrows, brass and earrings made of bronze and silver, and beads. [4, p. 86] During the Bronze Age and its later stages, the relations between cattle-breeders and settlers were also active in the Fergana Valley. This process of activation can be observed in the interaction of the inhabitants of the settlements and steppes, in the objects of material culture, in the construction of dwellings and cemeteries.

There are different views on the historical chronological date of the Kayrakkum culture, which has been assessed by researchers as a Fergana variant of the Andronovo historical-cultural unit. For example, N.A. Avanesova considered the Kayrakkum culture to belong to the XII-IX centuries BC [1, p.12], E.E. Kuzmina concluded that it belonged to the end of the second millennium BC - the beginning of the first millennium [6, p.42]. N.G. Gorbunova concluded that the Kayrakkum culture dates back to the 12th century BC [3, p. 23-46].

Archaeologist A.M. Mendelstam studied the Tulkhor culture, a Bronze Age nomadic pastoral culture in the Bishkent Valley of southern Tajikistan. In his research, the scientist gave a lot of information about the methods of burial of corpses in the graves of this culture, the tools of labor around them, the dishes, military weapons [9, p. 81].

The middle part of the ancient Yaksart and the surroundings of the basin have become an economic zone for cattle breeders. The tributaries of the Syrdarya: Inkordarya, Jonidarya, Kuvondarya, Eskidarya and the tributary of the Amudarya: Akchadarya play an important role in this area. In the northern regions of the Syrdarya basin in the X-VIII centuries BC were settled cattle-farming tribes. The tombs of these tribes have been studied by archaeologists. The economic culture of the pastoral tribes in this area is known as the name "Jetiasar culture". The Jetiasar culture lasted until the VIII-VII-IX centuries BC [7, p. 35]. In the lower reaches of the Syrdarya, large settlements and tombs of the Sak tribes of the VII-V centuries BC were studied.

The areas inhabited by nomadic pastoralists were larger than the areas of sedentary farming. However, due to the lack of pastures for pastoralists, they began to move towards the settled population. Thus, due to the threat of attack by cattle-breeding tribes, the settled population was forced to build defensive system towns and villages. Nomadic pastoralists of the lower reaches of the Syrdarya River were abandoned by pastoralists in the IV-II centuries BC due to drastic changes in water supply. For example, historical sources state that the inhabitants of Chirikrabort migrated to the south-west and south-east. In the Middle Syrdarya basin, the culture of cattle-breeding was active in ancient times. The Otrar-Aris and Kaunchi cultures were formed in the Otrar-Karatov region. The valleys of the South Kazakhstan and Aris and Talos rivers have become economic areas for livestock breeders.

In conclusion, a large part of the territory of Central Asia was formed by foothills, steppe zones, and this region was suitable for animal husbandry. From ancient times, as a result of migration of nomadic tribes and their cultural and economic ties with the settled population, nomadic pastoral cultures were formed in these areas. The study of these cultures serves as an important source in illuminating the ancient history of Central Asia. Central Asia's rich landscape of foothills and steppes has historically supported extensive nomadic pastoral cultures. The historiography of these cultures reveals a complex tapestry of migration, cultural exchange, and adaptation. Continued research and debate among scholars are crucial for a comprehensive understanding of the ancient history of Central Asia.

REFERENCES:

1. Аванесова Н. Проблема истории Андроновского культурного единстве. Автореф.кан.ист.наук, Л-Д, 1929, с.12

2. Асқаров А. Ўзбек халқининг келиб чиқиш тарихи. Тошкент. 2015.
3. Горбунова Н.Г. Кугайски-Карабулакская культура Ферганы // СА, №3, 1983, с.23-46
4. Дуке Х. Тябугузские поселения бургулюкской культуры Т «Фан», 1982.
5. Заднепровский Ю.А. Чустская культура Ферганы и памятники раннежелезного века Средней Азии. Автореф. дисс. Док ист наук. М, 1978
6. Кузмина Е.Е. Металлические изделия энеолита и бронзового века в Средней Азии / САИ, Вып. В 4-9. 1966, с.42
7. Левина Л.М. К истории исследований Хорезмской археолого-этнографической экспедиции в Восточном Приаралье. // Приаралье в дневном и средневековье М. 1998.
8. Максимова А.Г. Могильник Жамантогай / Древности Чардары/ Алма-Аты. 1968, с175-176.
9. Мандельштам А.М. Памятники эпохи бронзы в Южном Таджикистане. Ми А, №73, М. 1959.
10. Сариниди В.И. Юго-Западная Азия: Миграции, арии Зороастрийцы // ИБМАИКЦА // Вып-13 М. 1987 с 57-58.
11. Тереножкин А.И. Клад андроновских бронзовых предметов из с Бурчмула близ Ташкента //СА, №3, 1962, с.270-281
12. Толстов С. П. Древний Хорезм. М. Наука, 1948 с.66-68. Низовья Амударьи, Сарыкамьш, Узбой. 1960. с.89-119. МХЭ, Вып-3.; Толстов С.П., Итина М.А. История степных племен Южного Приаралья // ТХАЭЭ, Т.Х.М., 1977